

Reactivity of N-heterocyclic carbene, 1,3-bis(2,6-diisopropylphenyl)imidazol-2-ylidene, towards heavier halogens (Br₂ and I₂)

Shiv Pal, Meghna A. Manae, Vikas V. Khade and Shabana Khan*

Department of Chemistry, Indian Institute of Science Education and Research Pune, Dr. Homi Bhaba Road, Pashan, Pune-411 008, Maharashtra, India

E-mail: shabana@iiserpune.ac.in

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In the present study, the stoichiometry variation of N-heterocyclic carbene (NHC), **1** with halogens (Br₂ and I₂) shows its reactivity pattern toward halogens. The NHC, **1** was treated with 2.0, 1.0 and 0.5 equivalent of I₂ to afford the complex **2**, **3** and **4** respectively. In the same fashion, the treatment of **1** with 2.0 and 1.0 equivalent of Br₂ resulted in the formation of complexes **5** and **6**.

Keywords: NHCs, X-ray crystallography, DFT, NHCs adducts, halogens.

Introduction

Being a strong σ -donor and weak π -acceptor, N-heterocyclic carbenes (NHCs) paved the path for development of a new era of coordination chemistry, homogeneous catalysis and low valent chemistry of *p*-block elements¹. The chemistry of NHCs was pioneered by Fisher and coworkers in 1964², long before its isolation as a free carbene by Arduengo *et al.* in 1991³, and the first authentication of a carbene-metal complex by Öfele in 1968⁴. As soon as its sigma donor property was recognized, it has begun to replace conventional donor ligands i.e. phosphine, amine etc. in transition metal chemistry. Moreover, the strong σ -donor properties of NHCs were also exploited to realize unusual compounds with low valent *p*-block elements⁵. As the NHCs are primarily nucleophilic in nature, they form dative bonds with the electrophilic center i.e. metal and low valent species⁶. Along with metal complexes of NHCs, several reports on their complexes with non-metallic *p*-block species like BH₃, BF₃, CO₂ and I₂ are also available⁷⁻¹¹. The NHC-borane complexes could be synthesized by direct complexation of free NHC with borane precursor (**A** and **B**)⁸ or by treating the imidazolium salt (NHCs precursors) with a base, i.e. LiBEt₃H which also provides borane group (**C**)⁹. The selected examples of NHC-borane complexes are listed in the Chart 1. The dative bond between NHCs and borane could be considered as a covalent bond, and hence it does not show the classical hydroboration

Chart 1. Selected examples of NHC complexes with non-metallic *p*-block species.

reactions of alkene unlike the commercially available ether- or amine-borane adducts⁷. Like NHC-borane complexes,

NHCs form complexes with CO₂ by donation to the moderately electrophilic carbon center (**D**) (Chart 1). In 2004, Duong *et al.* showed the reversible carboxylation of NHCs, and they synthesized the NHCs-CO₂ complexes^{10a}. In 2006, Delaude and co-workers used NHC-CO₂ adducts as NHC's precursor for the synthesis of ruthenium complexes^{10b}. The NHC-CO₂ complexes have been successfully employed in the synthesis of useful products like methanol, urea, lactones etc.¹¹. As we have discussed so far, the reactivity of NHCs with *p*-block elements has been extensively studied, but surprisingly the reactivity towards halogens remained cursory. In 1991, Arduengo *et al.* reported the adduct of NHC and iodopentafluorobenzene and later, in 1994, the same group isolated the adduct of mesityl substituted NHC (IMes) and iodine (**E**)¹². In all these studies, the reactivity of NHCs was probed only towards iodine, while the other halogens (Cl₂, F₂, Br₂) remained neglected. Recently, Stack and coworkers reported the NHC halogen complexes [(IPr-X)⁺ (X = Cl, Br, I) (Chart 1, **F** and **2**)] prepared from the reductive elimination of IPr-CuX (IPr: 1,3-bis(2,6-diisopropylphenyl)imidazol-2-ylidene)¹³. Herein we report the reactivity of IPr towards I₂ as well as Br₂. These iodo- and bromo-adducts could be used as catalysts for the activation of imines and carbonyl dienophiles in Diels-Alder reactions¹⁴, cross-enolate coupling reactions¹⁵ and Michael addition reactions¹⁶.

Experimental

1. Materials and physical measurements

All manipulations were carried out in an inert gas atmosphere of dinitrogen using standard Schlenk techniques and in a dinitrogen filled glove box. The solvents (toluene, THF and pentane) used were purified by a MBRAUN solvent purification system MB SPS-800. Acetonitrile was distilled over CaH₂ before use. The IPr was synthesised following the method reported in literature¹⁷. All chemicals purchased from Aldrich were used without further purification. ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra were recorded in DMSO-*d*₆ using Bruker 400 MHz spectrometer. NMR spectra were referenced to external SiMe₄ (¹H and ¹³C). Mass spectra were recorded using AB Sciex, 4800 plus MALDI TOF/TOF spectrometer.

2. Synthesis of IPr-iodine complexes **2**, **3** and **4**

2.1. Synthesis of **2**:

0.388 g (1.0 mmol) of IPr was taken in 100 ml Schlenk flask with 40 ml of toluene. In the solution of IPr, 0.508 g (2.0

mmol) of I₂ was added at room temperature. The reaction mixture was stirred for 6 h. The dark brown precipitate of **2** was observed. The solution was decanted and the precipitate was dried under vacuum. Crystallization of **2** was done in acetonitrile. Yield: 0.845 g (95%). m.p. 168°C; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆, ppm): δ 8.8 (s, 2H, -CH=CH-), 7.7–7.5 (m, 6H, Ph), 2.16 (sept, *J* = 6.7 Hz, 4H, -CH-), 1.21 (d, *J* = 6.9 Hz, 12H, -CH₃), 1.18 (d, *J* = 6.8 Hz, 12H, -CH₃); ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆, ppm): δ 145.2, 132.2, 129.2, 125.6, 29.5, 24.6, 23.2. MALDI MS *m/z* 515.14 [M]⁺.

Note: The complex **2** can also be achieved via complex **3**. For this, 0.362 g (0.5 mmol) of **3** was taken in the flask with THF and then 0.127 g (0.5 mmol) of I₂ was added to the solution.

2.2. Synthesis of **3**:

0.388 g (1.0 mmol) of IPr was taken in 40 ml of toluene and subsequently 0.254 g I₂ (1.0 mmol) was added at room temperature. The pale yellow precipitate was observed during the stirring of 6 h. The reaction mixture was filtered and the precipitate of **3** was dried under vacuum. The recrystallization was done in acetonitrile. Yield: 0.580 g (91 %). m.p. 293 °C; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆, ppm): δ 8.73 (s, 2H, -CH=CH-), 7.72–7.59 (m, 6H, Ph), 2.23 (sept, *J* = 6.8 Hz, 4H, -CH-), 1.27 (d, *J* = 6.9 Hz, 12H, -CH₃), 1.23 (d, *J* = 6.8 Hz, 12H, -CH₃); ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆, ppm): δ 145.15, 132.58, 132.34, 128.46, 125.49, 29.38, 24.54, 23.25. MALDI MS *m/z* 641.09 [M]⁺. Elemental analysis (%): Calcd. C, 50.48; H, 5.65; N, 4.36. Found: C, 50.7; H, 5.57; N, 4.18.

2.3. Synthesis of **4**:

The same process, which was adopted for synthesis of **2** and **3**, was followed for the synthesis of **4** [0.776 g (2.0 mmol) IPr and 0.254 g (1.0 mmol) I₂ was taken for the reaction]. The crystallization of **4** was done in THF/pentane mixture. Yield: 0.810 g (90 %). m.p. 224°C; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆, ppm): δ 7.86 (s, 4H, -CH=CH-), 7.52–7.22 (m, 12H, Ph), 2.11 (sept, *J* = 6.9 Hz, 8H, -CH-), 1.03 (d, *J* = 6.8 Hz, 24H, -CH₃), 0.82 (d, *J* = 6.9 Hz, 24H, -CH₃); ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆, ppm): δ 155.15, 144.49, 133.41, 130.60, 124.11, 28.38, 24.13, 23.31. MALDI MS *m/z* 903.48 [M-I]⁺. Elemental analysis (%): Calcd. C, 62.91; H, 7.04; N, 5.43. Found: C, 63.45; H, 7.29; N, 5.08.

Note: The complex **4** can also be synthesised by treating the 0.160 g (0.25 mmol) of **3** with 0.25 mmol 0.97 g of IPr.

3. Synthesis of IPr-bromine complexes **5** and **6**

3.1. Synthesis of **5**:

In the Schlenk flask, 0.776 g (2.0 mmol) IPr was dissolved in 40 ml of toluene and 0.09 mL (4.0 mmol) Br₂ was added to this solution at room temperature. After stirring for 6 h, the solvent was decanted and dark orange precipitate was dried under vacuum. The recrystallization was done in acetonitrile. Yield: 0.680 g (96%). m.p. 252°C; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆, ppm): δ 8.88 (s, 2H, -CH=CH-), 7.76–7.62 (m, 6H, Ph), 2.26 (m, 4H, -CH-), 1.27 (d, *J* = 6.7 Hz, 12H, -CH₃), 1.23 (d, *J* = 6.9 Hz, 12H, -CH₃); ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆, ppm): δ 145.18, 133.01, 130.22, 128.29, 125.72, 29.43, 24.31, 23.33. MALDI MS: *m/z* 467.17 [M-Br₃]⁺.

Note: To synthesize **5** from **6**, 0.548 g (1.0 mmol) of **6** was taken in 40 mL of toluene and then 0.045 mL (1.0 mmol) of Br₂ was added to the solution.

3.2. Synthesis of **6**:

To the solution of 0.776 g (2.0 mmol) IPr in toluene, 0.045 mL Br₂ (1.0 mmol) was added. The reaction mixture was stirred for 6 h and then solvent was decanted and the white precipitate was dried under vacuum. The recrystallization was done in acetonitrile. Yield: 0.470 g (85%). m.p. 225°C; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆, ppm): δ 8.80 (s, 2H, -CH=CH-), 7.70–7.60 (m, 6H, Ph), 2.20 (m, 4H, -CH-), 1.21 (d, *J* = 6.8 Hz, 12H, -CH₃), 1.17 (d, *J* = 6.9 Hz, 12H, -CH₃); ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆, ppm): δ 145.2, 133.1, 130.3, 128.3, 128.0, 125.8, 29.5, 24.3, 23.4. MALDI MS: *m/z* 547.10 [M]⁺.

4. X-Ray crystallography details

Crystal data for all the IPr-halogen complexes, **2-6**, were collected on a Bruker Smart Apex Duo diffractometer at 100 K using Mo K α radiation (λ = 0.71073 Å). Data were corrected for absorption effect using multi-scan method (SADABS)¹⁸. The structures of **2-6** were solved by direct methods and refined by full-matrix least squares methods against F₂ (SHELXL-2014/7).

5. Computational

Structures of all compounds have been optimized using coordinates from XRD data as a starting point. The B3LYP DFT functional has been used, along with the LANL2DZ basis set for I and Br, to account for relativistic effects in a computationally efficient manner, and the 6-31G* basis set for all other atoms¹⁹. Frequency calculations were performed on all the stationary points that were optimized, and positive

frequencies were obtained ensuring that they were indeed minima. All calculations were carried out using the Gaussian 09 suite of programs²⁰.

Results and discussion

The reactions of IPr (**1**) with the required equivalent of respective halogens in the toluene resulted in a variety of NHC-halogens complexes (**2-6**). The crystallization of **2**, **3**, **5** and **6** was done in acetonitrile, while for the crystallization of complex **4**, THF-pentane mixture (in 1:1 ratio) was used. The tentative mechanism for the synthesis of IPr-halogens complexes is given in Scheme S1 (see Supporting Information). In the case of 1:1 stoichiometric ratio, we assume that the IPr attacks the one halogen (X = Br, I) atom leading to the cleavage of X-X bond and formation of **3** and **6** in which the halogen counter anion is loosely bound to the other halogen atom (Case I). If two equivalents of halogen are added to the reaction mixture, the loosely bound counter anion in **3** and **6** react with another molecule of the halogen leading to the formation of complexes **2** and **5** (Case II). If two equivalents of NHCs are used, then it attacks the positively polarized halogen of 1:1 complexes, leading to the dicoordinated iodonium cation, **4** (Case III). It is worth to mention here that neither the reaction of **2** eq. of IPr with Br₂ nor the treatment of **6** with IPr afforded the complex, analogous to **4**. The ¹H spectra of complexes, **3** and **6** show doublets, for CH₃ proton at δ 1.27–1.23 and 1.21–1.17 ppm respectively, and a septet around δ 2.23 and 2.20 ppm, respectively, for the CH proton of isopropyl group. The ¹H signal for the alkene proton appears at δ 8.73 (**3**) and 8.80 (**6**) ppm which are shifted downfield when compared to that of IPr. In the ¹H spectrum of **4**, doublet peaks for CH₃ protons resonate at δ 1.02 and 0.82 ppm, and the signal for CH and CH=CH appears at δ 2.11 and 7.86 ppm, respectively. The molecular structures of **2** and **5** are given in the Supporting information, and their structural parameters are comparable to the structures reported by Stack and coworkers (**F** and **2**)¹³. The IPr-iodine complexes, **3** and **4**, crystallize in the orthorhombic space-group *Pbca* and the tetragonal space-group *I41cd*, respectively¹⁸. The molecular structures of **3** (Fig. 1) and **6** (Fig. 3) reveal the presence of a loosely bound iodide and bromide counter anion, respectively. The I⋯I interaction in complex **3** and the Br⋯Br interaction in complex **6** are of 3.22 and 3.14 Å, respectively, and these lengths are much longer than their respective covalent bond lengths [I-I in I₂ (2.67 Å) and Br-Br

Fig. 1. The molecular structure of **3**·2MeCN at the thermal ellipsoid's probability level of 50%. The hydrogen atoms and MeCN molecules are omitted for clarity. The selected bond length (Å) and bond angles (degree); Calculated geometrical parameters are given in brackets: C1-N1 1.328(7) [1.355], C1-N2 1.346(7) [1.355], C1-I1 2.128(4) [2.319], I1-I2 3.2150(8) [3.137]; C1-I1-I2 177.4(2) [180.0].

in Br₂ (2.28 Å)]. The molecular structure of **4** is shown in Fig. 2. The average C_{carbene}-I bond distance in **4** is 2.33 Å, which is longer than the C-I bond distance (2.07 Å) reported for **2**¹³. The C1-I1-C2 bond angle is 178.8° which shows linear geometry around the I⁺ like that in I₃⁻.

Structures of all compounds have been optimized using coordinates from XRD data as a starting point. The B3LYP DFT functional has been used, along with the LANL2DZ basis set for I and Br, to account for relativistic effects in a

Fig. 2. The molecular structure of **4**·THF at the thermal ellipsoid's probability level of 50%. The hydrogen atoms and THF molecule are omitted for clarity. The selected bond length (Å) and bond angles (degree); Calculated geometrical parameters are given in brackets: C1-I1 2.302(7) [2.400], C2-I1 2.363(7) [2.395], C1-N1 1.35(1) [1.357], C1-N2 1.36(1) [1.358], C2-N3 1.35(1) [1.358], C2-N4 1.33(1) [1.358]; C1-I1-C2 178.8(3) [179.8].

Scheme 1. Synthesis of IPr-halogen complexes.

computationally efficient manner, and the 6-31G* basis set for all other atoms¹⁹. Frequency calculations were performed on all the stationary points that were optimized, and positive frequencies were obtained ensuring that they were indeed minima. All calculations were carried out using the Gaussian 09 suite of programs²⁰. For **2**, **3**, **5** and **6**, the structures were successfully optimized taking initial guess from XRD data and all the geometrical parameters are matching well with the experimental values except for the C1-I1-I2 angle in **3**, Br1-Br2 bond and C1-Br1-Br2 angle in **6** which are slightly different from the experimental values.

Fig. 3. The molecular structure of **6**·MeCN at the thermal ellipsoid's probability level of 50%. The hydrogen atoms and MeCN are omitted for clarity. The selected bond length (Å) and bond angles (degree); Calculated geometrical parameters are given in brackets: Br1-Br2 3.1393(6) [2.794], C1-Br1 1.856(4) [2.151], N1-C1 1.344(5) [1.351], N2-C1 1.325(5) [1.352]; C1-Br1-Br2 172.0(1) [180.0].

In case of **4**, it was not possible to obtain the correct geometry even after several attempts, i.e. after optimization, the distance between I and the two NHC ligands was not in accordance with the experimental values. To remedy this, we used a bottom-up approach, by adding the substituents on the ligand in small steps. In this manner, we were able to obtain a minimum energy structure where the distance between I and the two NHC ligands was almost equal to the distance seen in the XRD data (see Computational details in Supporting information). We tried the same bottom-up approach to optimize [(IPr)₂Br]⁺[Br]⁻, bromine analogue of **4** as well. This approach ended with the structure where Br⁺ is separated from both the IPr by 2.03 and 2.69 Å, respectively.

We hypothesize that the additional steric hindrance brought on by the isopropyl groups prevents the formation of [(IPr)₂Br]⁺[Br]⁻. This is also supported by the fact that we were unable to synthesis this complex despite extensive efforts.

Further, to check whether these IPr-halogen complexes show the reversible behaviours like IPr-CO₂ reported by Duong *et al.*^{10a}, we performed the Thermo-gravimetric Analysis (TGA) (Fig. 4). None of the complexes show the clear loss of halogen, and they decompose as a whole.

Fig. 4. Thermogravimetric Analysis curves of IPr-halogen complexes (**1-6**).

All the complexes show higher thermal stability as compared to IPr. The complexes **2** and **5** begin to decompose around 170–180°C and 250–260°C, respectively. In the TGA curves of **3** and **6**, a clean respective weight loss of 10% and 5% was observed which corresponds to the mass of acetonitrile (solvent of crystallization). Similarly, **4** shows a weight loss of 6% for the elimination of THF between 110 to 140°C.

Conclusions

In summary, we have successfully showed the reactivity pattern of IPr towards I₂ and Br₂ in various stoichiometric ratio. The stoichiometry of the reaction determines the composition of the products. In 1:1 mixture, simple mono-coordinated halogen cation with loosely bound halide atom as counteranion is achieved (**3** and **6**). When excess halogen is used, NHC halogen cations with trihalide counter an-

ions are obtained (**2** and **5**), while the use of excess NHC led to dicoordinated linear iodonium cation (**6**). The TGA analyses showed that all the complexes reported have higher thermal stability as compared to IPr (**1**). Currently, we are studying the reactivity of these cations in halogenation reactions, in which these cations can be the active halogenating agents.

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Supporting information

Supporting information contains NMR data, crystallographic details and molecular structures of **2** and **5**.

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